

Deliverable 8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan: Matrix Update

Blue-Action: Arctic Impact on Weather and Climate is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon 2020 Work programme topics addressed: BG-10-2016 Impact of Arctic changes on the weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere. Start date: 1 December 2016. End date: 1 March 2021.

The Blue-Action project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 727852.

Blue-Action Deliverable D8.1

About this document

Deliverable: D8.1

Work package in charge: WP8 Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, and Exploitation

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: Project-month 3

Dissemination level: General Public

Lead author(s)

SAMS Research Services Ltd (SRSL): Raeanne Miller

Other contributing author(s)

Climate-KIC Aps (CKIC): Peter Vangsbo

Reviewer(s)

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI): Chiara Bearzotti

We support the Blue Growth!

Visit us on: www.blue-action.eu

Follow us on Twitter: [@BG10Blueaction](https://twitter.com/BG10Blueaction)

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Index

Summary for publication 4

Work carried out..... 5

Main results achieved 6

Progress beyond the state of the art 6

Impact..... 6

Lessons learned and links built 7

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action 8

References (Bibliography) 8

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results 8

 Dissemination Activities 8

 Peer Reviewed Articles..... 8

 Other Publications..... 8

 The Communication and Dissemination Matrix is attached to this document. 8

 Uptake by the targeted audiences 8

 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable..... 9

Summary for publication

The original Communication and Dissemination Matrix included as part of the Blue Action Description of Action (Table 2.2 a1) has been updated to reflect an improved project description, project partner ambitions, and an improved assessment of stakeholder, industry, policy, and general public engagement pathways. The matrix has been developed to ensure that we “promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner” (Art 38.1 of the Grant Agreement).

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix update was carried out by SAMS Research Services Ltd (SRSL), with input from Climate-KIC. The matrix will form the basis of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D.8.4), and will form the basis of Blue Action’s communication activities going forwards. The matrix will be reviewed regularly to ensure that we continue to communicate with our targeted audiences.

Work carried out

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix set out in the Blue Action Description of Action was presented to all project partners at the Blue Action project kick-off meeting held in Berlin, January 18th-20th, 2017, as part of an overall presentation of work package 8 by SAMS Research Services Ltd (SRSL). Throughout the meeting, feedback was solicited by SRSL and Climate-KIC from project partners with regards to their contacts, stakeholder networks, and key messages for communications. This feedback was then compiled and reviewed by SRSL and Climate-KIC following the kick-off meeting, and incorporated into both the Communication and Dissemination Matrix (this deliverable), and the project communication plan (D 8.4).

Review of Target Audiences

The set of target audiences for dissemination and communication were reviewed by SRSL. The target audiences outlined in the revised Communication and Dissemination Matrix include:

Target Audience
National and European governments Policy makers European Commission services
Indigenous communities (Sami and Inuit)
Environmental NGOs (such as Greenpeace and BirdLife International)
Business sector end users (emerging business actors and established business actors)
Specialist and wider scientific community
European and international initiatives and projects (such as Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance, Year of Polar Prediction, Copernicus World Climate Research Programme)
Higher education course leaders and Meteorological Office Training facilities delivering climate science
Public and wider society interested in science projects and results, and/or climate change research
Project partners

Of these, the Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance was re-categorized within *European and international initiatives and projects*, recognizing that it is a coordinated international initiative focussed on “increasing our knowledge of the Atlantic Ocean and its dynamic systems – including interlinks with the portion of the Arctic region that borders the Atlantic and to promote the sustainable management of its resources”. We distinguished these international research initiatives from policy-related audiences as the communication objectives and messages are different, the former focussing on knowledge sharing and synchronisation of activities while the latter focusses on policy-relevant results and evidence-based decision making.

Review of Communication Objectives, Content, and Tools

For each target audience, communication objectives, content and tools were reviewed and amended by SRSL. In most cases, communication objectives were redefined to ensure that they clearly reflected the aim or goal of communication with and dissemination to each target audience. Similarly, content and messages were revised in order to be discrete and more specifically targeted towards each audience, based on their perceived needs. Tools described in the matrix were also defined with greater specificity to reflect concrete activities to be carried out over the duration of the project. These will be further elaborated in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.4).

Review of Expected Frequency and Responsibilities

No changes were made to the frequency and assignment of responsibility for each item in the matrix. The frequency of specific deliverables remains unchanged.

Main results achieved

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix has been updated. Target audiences have been reviewed, and communication objectives, content, and tools have been revised to reflect greater specificity towards target audiences.

Progress beyond the state of the art

Not applicable.

Impact

How has this work contributed to the expected impacts of Blue Action?

The revised Communication and Dissemination Matrix is now available to project partners, and will guide the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.4). In doing so, the matrix contributes to the wider visibility of the project, ensuring that the project and its outcomes are widely shared. In combination with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.4), it provides a consistent baseline for activities carried out in WP8, and a common approach to and understanding of project communication, dissemination, and exploitation across the entire Blue Action partnership.

With the information in the Communication and Dissemination Matrix, we will contribute to the achievement of the following expected impacts:

- Enhance the response capacity of specific stakeholders in the Northern Hemisphere by delivering in an open dialogue with specific end-users the results of the research activities to the society and testing the value of the climate services through joint activities with societal players (business, policy makers, NGOs, indigenous communities)
- Improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change, including business stakeholders, Inuit and Sami community, policy makers at a European Level, environmental NGOs
- Improve the uptake of measurements from satellites by making use of new Earth observation assets
- Improve the capacity to respond to the impact of climatic change on the environment

Blue-Action Deliverable D8.1

and human activities in the Arctic, both in the short and longer term

- Contribute to the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) and IPCC scientific assessments, and to the Copernicus Climate Change (C3S) services via the mutual exchange of information on on-going and planned research activities of each participant
- Improving innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge
- Improve the professional skills and competences for those working and being trained to work within this subject area

Impact on the Business Sector

With the information in the Communication and Dissemination Matrix, we will contribute to the achievement of the following expected impacts:

- Interaction with business stakeholders will be enhanced by testing the delivering of new downstream products and services
- Improve business stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change
- Improve the capacity to respond to the impact of climatic change on human activities in the Arctic, both in the short and longer term
- Contribute to better servicing the economic sectors that rely on improved forecasting capacity (e.g. shipping, mining)
- Improving innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge
- Strengthening the competitiveness and growth of companies by developing innovations meeting the needs of European and global markets; and, where relevant, by delivering such innovations to the markets

Lessons learned and links built

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix forms the basis for the communication and dissemination strategy of Blue Action. It identifies our target audiences and specifies the specific content and messages for each audience. In developing this communication matrix, we recognize that it may need to be reviewed and amended as the project progresses, in order to remain current and effective for all target audiences.

This deliverable is directly linked to Deliverable 8.4 (Communication and Dissemination Plan), as the objectives, content, and tools for communication, dissemination, and exploitation outlined in the matrix will be further detailed in D8.4.

By targeting governments, policymakers, and European Commission services, we intend to develop links with their activities in order to inform policy and decision making. Two-way interaction with indigenous communities and environmental NGOs through the Societal Engagement Group, as outlined in this matrix and in deliverables 8.6-8.11, will ensure the ongoing relevance of Blue Action's activities to stakeholder groups.

The matrix outlines our approach to 'clustering' (WP6) with European and international initiatives and projects, and includes joint activities planned in WP6.

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action

By fostering communication among project partners, and between project partners and the wider scientific community, businesses, NGOs, policymakers, and indigenous community stakeholders, this deliverable contributes to the achievement of all the objectives and specific goals indicated in the Description of the Action, part B, Section 1.1.

Specifically, the Communication and Dissemination Matrix will be a tool for achieving Objectives 7 and 8:

- **Objective 7 Fostering the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting their economic growth**
- **Objective 8 Transferring knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders**

This will be achieved by carrying out the activities outlined in the Communication and Dissemination Matrix, in combination with those to be outlined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.4).

References (Bibliography)

- European Commission, “Communicating EU Research and Innovation, A guidance for project participants, Version 1.0”, EU Publications Office, Luxembourg, 2014
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation European Commission, PowerPoint presentation on “Communicating Horizon 2020 projects” Alexandra Ruete, 2015
- European IPR Helpdesk, PowerPoint presentation on “Managing H2020 projects to maximise impact and innovation”, Dr. Eugene Sweeney, 8 July 2015

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results

Dissemination Activities

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix has been used as a basis for the forthcoming Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.4). In its draft version, it was presented at the Blue Action kick-off meeting in Berlin, Jan 18-20, 2017. The Communication and Dissemination Matrix will be made accessible on the Blue Action website, www.blueaction.eu.

Peer Reviewed Articles

Not applicable for this deliverable.

Other Publications

The Communication and Dissemination Matrix is attached to this document.

Uptake by the targeted audiences

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
---	-------------------------

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audiences:

Blue-Action Deliverable D8.1

Matrix will be made accessible on the Blue Action website, www.blueaction.eu.

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.

Deliverable 8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan: Matrix Update

Target Audience	Objectives	Content / Message	Tools	Expected frequency	Responsibility
National and European governments Policy makers European Commission services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform future climate policy • Encourage evidence-based decision-making using project outputs • Contribute to international committees (e.g. IPCC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project progress and results • Policy relevance of project and results • Demonstration of tools for greater understanding of the impact of Arctic changes on the weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written policy briefings to Members of European Parliament • Face to face contact, for example via existing members of e.g. IPCC steering groups / EU committees 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP8, Project office
Indigenous communities (Sami and Inuit)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solicit critical feedback on project outcomes • Inform opportunities for climate adaptation • Ensure maximum societal benefit from research • Raise awareness of project & climate change impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project results and implications tailored for a broader non specialist audience • Active feedback from the communities involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Print & online content tailored to a non-specialist audience • Direct engagement with and feedback from Societal Engagement Group (SEG) 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP8, Project office
Environmental NGOs Such as Greenpeace and BirdLife	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solicit critical feedback on project outcomes • Encourage uptake of improved climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project results and implications tailored for a broader non specialist audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Print & online content tailored to a non-specialist audience 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP8, Project office

Target Audience	Objectives	Content / Message	Tools	Expected frequency	Responsibility
	information for societal awareness and action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active feedback from the NGOs involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement with and feedback from Societal Engagement Group (SEG) 		
Business sector end users (emerging business actors and established business actors)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage a wide variety of relevant industry with project & outcomes to maximise societal benefit Ensure project outcomes are relevant and in a useable format through co-design Create market demand for any products/services developed Ensure weather-dependent industries quickly understand the project objectives and outcomes as they apply to their business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results and implications tailored for an industry audience End user products and services available Identified opportunities for further partnership or collaboration with business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Case studies and reports of these (WP5) Print, online, & social media content tailored to a business audience Direct engagement via roadshow and/or 'meet and pitch' Panel discussions at relevant business events Project /product /service specification sheets 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP5 and WP 8, Project Office All partners
Specialist and wider scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange knowledge Maximise impact and exploitation of project outcomes through collaboration Integration of the project with other projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project progress and results Opportunities for collaboration and idea development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific conferences and project annual meetings Peer-reviewed journal articles Up-to-date website content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular publication of scientific findings (open access) Annual project meetings 	WP6, WP8, Project office, All partners
European and international initiatives and projects such as Transatlantic Ocean	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure synchronisation of activities for addressing open science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project progress and results Share-able resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular online and face to face communication 	See WP6 planned deliverables	WP6, Project Office

Target Audience	Objectives	Content / Message	Tools	Expected frequency	Responsibility
Research Alliance, YOPP, Copernicus World Climate research programme	<p>questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a shared understanding of the project and results Demonstrate the value added through collaborative working 	<p>with applicability across initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunities for feedback from the communities involved 	<p>(two-way) with new and existing projects and initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint activities planned in WP6 such as Gap Maps Joint-seminars and contribution to specific deliverables 		
Higher education course leaders and Meteorological Office training facilities delivering climate science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure knowledge is passed on through education Improve the professional skills and competencies of those working in the specific topic areas covered by the project, Tackling skills gap of workforce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to date Arctic climate and weather information as it relates to project progress and results Content based on open access to publications and data, tailored to this audience Opportunities to engage further with the project & its partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Face-to-face engagement with existing higher education & training facilities & networks Co-development of knowledge resources, for example: training modules and webinars, online resources, recorded workshops & fact sheets 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP8, All, Project Office
Public and wider society interested in science projects and results, and/or climate change research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximise project visibility in wider society Ensure maximum societal benefit through the provision of improved climate information Raise awareness of Arctic climate change, modelling, and societal impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results and implications tailored for a broader non specialist audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website content Social Media (Twitter and other social media platforms) Public lectures and presentations Press releases and media coverage 	See WP8 planned deliverables	WP8, Project Office

Target Audience	Objectives	Content / Message	Tools	Expected frequency	Responsibility
Project partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure an effective and integrated project • Keep all partners actively involved in the project • Timely identify and protect any Intellectual Property 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and dissemination Plan • Ad-hoc communication opportunities & ideas • Progress and results of WP • Complementary research / project results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intranet • Web and teleconferencing • Project meetings • Work Package meetings 	Regular updates to intranet and email communications, Annual project meeting, , Quarterly video/tele-conference on scientific updates	Project office (WP7) and WP8

The Blue-Action project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 727852.